

THE BUSINESS TERMINOLOGY SUCH AS SPECIAL TERMS

Akramov Bekzod Qahramonovich

Bukhara State University

E-mail: bukhara.bek@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Terms and concepts organize the representation of the world and are part of relationships of contiguity, synonymy or even identity. Commercial job naming is no exception. But there is not one, but several terminologies. The company is the most representative witness to the evolution of terminology in this field, an evolution linked to the organization of the profession, the company and more generally society. Understanding the use, the motivation for the choice of these concepts, their dynamics, the type of relationship that unites them is a matter of socioterminology. Arriving at a consensual, non-reductive harmonization of concepts based on a field survey will lead to better knowledge sharing.

Key words: Concepts, sales, professions, terms, socioterminology.

Terminology language dictionary contained role about two outlook there is First to the idea according to the terminology literary language of the lexicon independent layer in the style of confession if possible, the second to the doctrine according to it is literary language word wealth from the composition separated, “separately standing” object in the style of is evaluated and of speech types (dialect, slang, lively conversation) to is equalized. V.P.Danilenko’s, terminology when you say general literature of the tongue independent functional type, that is traditional scientific language (science, science or technique language) means is caught. The language of science general literature of the tongue functional from systems one as live conversation language and artistic literature language concepts with one in line stands.

INTRODUCTION

The language of science of the nation general literature language based on is formed and develops. Therefore science, science language foundation general literature of the tongue lexicon, word to be made and grammar organize does by H. Hewell note to reach according to the terminology certain to science about terms or technique in the field applicable words is the sum. We terms the meaning note reach through they are representing also note the concepts. Term the word differently to understand there is for example, for logicians the term is clear to the object belongs to description (or descriptions) sum mean holder and in it app to be word is considered how in the

language desired word the term to be can Science and in technique the term is artificial thinking found or natural from the language received special word is counted. Such of words application field it or this scientific school representatives by is determined or is limited. Universal from the terms different like science, technology special terms hierarchical units as terminological to systems unite, they own to the meanings only the same system inside achieves this in the system to them logical (to concept about) terminological field suitable will come in science each how development, development scientific of terms surface output or from clarification a tree gives. Marked (marked) and unmarked units theory logical division development and in improvement new step is counted. In the 30s of the XX century with this issue closely engaged in Prague linguistic school (PLM) members (N.Trubetskoy, R.Yakobson) ideas in the 60s to the text using a machine (EHM). Processing to give, that is texts coding and recoding, data car using Search text one from the language another one to the language translation to do like in processes very productive the fact that proved. Unlabeled of units zero indexed, labeled of units while unmarked to units relatively addition information transportation in terms of differentiation was determined. Term and terminological lexicon concepts from each other differentiate necessary of terms application, distribution scope certain terminological system with limited they are of a person activity within sure in style movement does, happens. Terminological lexicon own a narrow specialty from within public communication to the circle moved unprofessional speech in context wide used word and word compounds cover takes Literary language to the circle past the term own terminology, terminological area and from the system distance, terminality from the characteristic separate remains.[1]

METHODS

Term definition in particular scientific in the literature from many - many considerations reported. Almost all in definitions the term special scientific and technical the concept expressive word or word compound in the style of is described of O.Vinokur according to the term - har always sure and obvious. Terms system language conscious is formed. After all, the term spontaneous, spontaneous way appear maybe not necessity in society to him need is created due to its existence. A.S. Gerd's to his judgment according to the term of the development of science certain stage there is of concepts main features sure and in full reflection bringer special terminological to the meaning have natural and artificial language unit, that is word or word is a combination. O.S. Akhmanova's, terminology some science of development higher level only when achieved surface comes out, that is the term certain concept sure scientific expression occupation from then recognized.

The term from my notary differentiate important tool him scientific basically describe possible it is not. V.G.Gak of the term definition to give line, his essence opens

and of the term something one language word wealth place determines. He is scientific at work to term dictionary of units separately type in the style of to be considered objection means and term-function, lexicon units of its application one looks like the idea before pushes. V.P. Danilenko confession in society happen to be each how of the process vision first in terminology own expression finds or certain of terms transformational change due to occurs. D.S. Lotte's in their work to term separately sign as not but sure of the system member of in the form of look, attitude to be necessity emphasized. [2] His to his opinion according to content in the plan systematic relationships of terms system to the character ownership determines of terms terms in the system place, position certain of understanding concepts in the system place, position with is determined. Terminology various districts school, scientific direction and sure to thoughts special categorical hardware representing, terms to the system united special concepts sum, set in the style of is considered.

RESULTS

Current in the day country of the economy development about very a lot affairs take is going Including economy development main from the joints one was tourism also in the field of changes witness we are Our president today's in the day tourism to the field about issuing decision and decrees this about shortcomings to fill and tourism country to scale take to exit big thrown away steps let's say exaggeration did not we will be Our opinion proof as "Uzbekistan Republic of tourism field fast development provide measures "about". Decree, Uzbekistan President of August 16, 2017 «2018-2019 tourism field development 1st order measures on "about"». Decision tourism in the field being done things new to stage raised. Tourism not only today's country in the eyes, maybe the Timurids to him in his time separately attention directed. That is the first tourists in Movarounnahr trips of Amir Temur and his descendants in the time activated. Tourism of the field the development is definitely internal economic of structures to improve, from this except that's it field with depends respectively activity take going of fields is also positive for development effect shows. But the journey make, constant to live out of place another Rest in place, new regions to see or healing in the regions health recovery for big financial funds Demand it is not a secret.

These funds necessary to the address arrived go, spend the night to stay and accommodation, food and that's it such as different from services used for is spent. Social to the defense needs population layers partially of the state social protection from politics use to the goal is appropriate. Developed countries this population groups special trips organize systems current done and they are through tourism services exactly of the population less provided layers service to do provided. Tourism touristic organizations by legal way done is increased. That's it see tourism one how many different to species separated: internal tourism, international tourism, hobby

tourism, business tourism, ecotourism, sport tourism, auto tourism, knowledge level expand for take to go tourism and others. Business tour tourist professional activity with depends income benefit get goals intended and to the law the opposite did not happen each how organizational, economic; commerce, business activity with depends trip type. Incoming tourism is specific state to the territory foreign fifty of tourists visit with done increasing tourism. Someone to the state coming tourists that's it area for incoming tourism subject is considered Internal tourism is something state in the area constant living population by that's it state of the territory another towards organized tourism. Internal the term tourism is the last in years wide in consumption applicable lexicon to unity turning around is going Social tourism-travel expenses state budget, from the budget except funds, work giver at the expense of complete or partially covered tourism.[3]

Complete Lexicon of Commercial vocabulary to become a leader in your commercial field, you must master the vocabulary of your theme. Become so comfortable with technical terms that your speech becomes devilishly powerful and impactful. For this, no secret, you must master all the terms related to selling and trading and use these words wisely.

You will win in:

- efficiency
- credibility
- authority

You do not yet imagine the power of words. Well- mastered trade terms can win you valuable contracts.

Through simple words.

Commercial Telephone Vocabulary

- **Cold call**

The cold call is the call made without prior preparation, on the spot. Without having had any contact before with his interlocutor.

- **Phoning**

Phoning is the action of calling a client-prospect list. A salesperson is in the phoning phase when he makes calls one after the other in order to advance in his commercial actions.

- **Prospecting**

Prospecting is the set of actions that aim to find new customers. It is about contacting prospects through different means. At program:

- contact telephone
- mail of email
- contact in direct

- research of contacts

The objective: to get an appointment to present your offer.[4]

- **Lock a Call/Call**

Locking a call means obtaining an appointment (or your initial call objective: an appointment, a callback, a contact) at the end of your phone call.

- **Secretary barrage**

The expression barrage secretary is used during telephone prospecting. It is common to call a reception telephone number (store or business) and have the secretary on line responsible for screening the calls. It transmits communications to interlocutors according to internal instructions with certain filters.

This is why some “secretary roadblocks” are tougher and more difficult than others to get your contact online.

You do not know the name of your interlocutor to contact, you are in the telephone prospecting phase. Obtain the name of the decision-maker of TrucMuche (kitchen accessories) and an appointment with him.

You call the TrucMuche company number. The secretary picks up, you announce this “Hello Madam, Mr Tartempion online. I would like to speak to the commercial manager of the south west area please”. The secretary replies "He is not available and does not make new contacts"...

What to answer to that? You can insist a little but at best the secretary who does her job well will tell you to send documentation by email to her address, which she will forward.

- **Prospect**

The prospect is the contact who is not yet your customer – who has not purchased anything from you. But to whom you have the opportunity to present your offer.

- **Make the opening – closing**

You are the person in charge of raising and lowering the store’s curtain. Very often you also take care of putting in order the sales stations, the lighting, the reserve, etc.

- **Merch – Merchandising**

Merchandising is the action of putting a shelf – a shelf in order. Bring the products on a shelf forward, for example, for a more pleasant visual and commercial effect.

This involves following an established organization to best enhance the products in the store.

- **Facing**

The facing is the visual of your shelf, your corner or your space. It is the visual marketing logic of your store, with general consistency.

- **Additional Sale**

Upselling is the act of selling a product or service in addition to your customer's original purchase.

To master additional or complementary selling like no one else, read this complete article .[5]

- Supply

The supply or replenishment consists of placing the orders necessary for the good performance of the stock. You must anticipate product releases – according to your forecast.

- Central Aisle

The central aisle is the sinews of war in a shopping centre.

This is the main aisle through which customers enter the sales area. It is wider than a classic department and very regularly offers promotions from the store.

- them offers catalog
- them promotions from moment
- them novelties

The central aisle is regularly renewed and reflects the commercial dynamics of the store.

- Cross Aisle

The cross aisle is the little sister of the central aisle.

It is actually the aisle perpendicular to the central aisle, which provides access to the other departments of the store.

Most of the time, the central aisle begins in the middle of the central aisle to serve the other departments from the left. It also makes it possible to highlight the Heads of Gondolas.

- Gondola Head

The end of a gondola or TG corresponds to the end of a radius – which is linear to it. The TG is therefore the end of the shelf, which is used to offer products – often highlighted – on the cross aisle.[6]

- Brief

The brief or briefing is given by the manager – of a department, a shop, a sector – and aims to communicate commercial information to the sales team.

It is a question of evoking the actions to be put in place, the objectives and keeping an eye on the actions in progress.

- Gerber (One Pallet)

Stacking a pallet consists of filming it and placing it high up in a reserve.

- Buyer

The buyer is your decision maker. Not necessarily your end customer (especially in B to B), but the one who decides on the purchase decision in store or in central purchasing on behalf of a brand.

The buyer can also be the head of the department in mass distribution or the sales manager also in B to B.

- Purchasing Center

A brand's purchasing center centralizes purchases on behalf of its multiple stores. By buying in bulk, it can drive prices down for the manufacturers it uses.

The purchasing center very often manages the logistics of the brand in order to centralize and harmonize everything (processes, prices, agreements).

- Markdown

In the popular sense, markdown is associated with sales.

Be careful however, in the commercial vocabulary the markdown is more precise. This is stock variance.

Between a theoretical stock and an actual stock recorded in inventory, 2 types of markdowns may appear.

1. Known markdown (problem on the product, breakage in store: any product inconsistency identified before inventory)
2. Unknown markdown (essential markdown: theft, loss, other... Where any explanation clearly identifiable is data)

- B to B

Selling from professional to professional, quite simply. B to B stands for "Business to Business".

Let me give you a few examples of this specific trading vocabulary.

Exercise in B to B one:

- sales to large retailers
- industrial spare parts seller
- maker of fabrics

- Skeleton

The Skeleton in the sale corresponds to goods offered during a first order. Common practice in certain activities, it is anecdotal or non-existent for others.

- Characteristic

The product characteristics are factual. They describe technical aspects of the product. Take the example of a bicycle. The characteristics will be:

- 28 inch wheels
- Stem of saddle in steel
- Crutch in steel
- Weight 12.2kg

Factual. Precise. Without analysis.

- Advantage

The advantages reflect comfort for the user. What is the advantage of this "weight 12.2 kg" feature?

Answer: The bike is light -compared to other models.

- Profit

The benefit, meanwhile, is the positive comfort that the characteristic will represent on a daily basis. To return to the example of the weight of the bike, the benefit here will be that pedaling is less tiring than with another model.

- Sales pitch

The sales pitch all your preparation work before a sales meeting.

It allows you to highlight the advantages, benefits and product characteristics during your sales meeting.

The pre-survey (questionnaires and interviews) is aimed at HRDs and sales managers responsible for designating positions and recruiting. (The global survey will also be aimed at field sales representatives). The questionnaires are divided into two parts. The first aims to know the designation of sales representatives in the company, for: field sales positions, sedentary sales representatives, positions of responsibility and development positions. The questionnaire is organized into 5 themes: the current title of the post, the missions and their content, the level of responsibility and hierarchy, the history of the title of the post, the criteria for choosing the current title. The second part is oriented on the global perception of designations focusing on two themes: the functions of the designation and the actual perception of predefined designations.

The results the analysis of the data (questionnaires returned, supplemented by interviews) aggregates 27 different headings and 24 designations concerning the immediate hierarchical superiors. It highlights elements, avenues for further reflection.

Titles A few examples of designations are grouped together in the table. The term manager predominates, it designates operational sales staff but also people in charge of management functions. The first positions in a company are generally marked by the term commercial (or attached) or even technical-commercial. The higher you go in the hierarchy, the more they disappear in favor of the term sales. High responsibility positions are characterized by three terms: director, leader or manager.

This degree of responsibility is measured in terms of geographic area coverage. Ambiguities appear: regional sales manager and regional sales manager. Director refers to the top of the hierarchical pyramid in the company, the concepts of leader and manager seem to coexist. But here again, the use of responsible increases, because it is more neutral than chief, the latter evoking the negative notion of authority.[7] The concepts of key account engineer, key account manager, key account engineer, key

account manager are equivalent. The concept of manager competes with that of engineer, which persists because it is based on the acquisition of an engineering degree.

CONCLUSION

These results give an overview of the scope of the research and serve to validate a work methodology. In addition, such a survey is long-term because it requires work in several stages. The evolution of terminology is linked to the reorganization of companies, which have repercussions on the commercial approach and the skills required. The concept of a commercial profession is above all a sector of activity and has long been associated with the designation of sales force (sales force technician). One could wonder about the extension of the concept because the notion of purchases is not taken into account. Commercial is used as a specific term but also belongs to the common language and metonymic shifts are numerous. We often talk about commercial function. We see the close limits between term and word. The specific designations then rather correspond to a function in the company. The criteria used (geographic sector, hierarchy, training, etc.) must also be taken into account when defining the term or concept. Proposing a common repository to different users, with the aim of harmonizing concepts and their understanding, of modeling knowledge would make it possible to compare data at the international level. We could then consider an ontology of the system of concepts. The creation of a tool could help companies find the designation that meets their needs and thus allow them to be more creative. They could thus be based on the scales of perception of the connotations of the terms.

REFERENCES:

1. Cartier E. & Isaac F. (2009). Word and automatic language processing, in *Modern French*, n°1, Paris, p 144-160
2. Depecker L. (2009). Between word and term: technicality in words, in «*Le français modern*», n°1, Paris, p.132-144
3. Gaudin F. (2003). *Socioterminology, a linguistic approach to terminology*, Brussels, Duculot De Boeck
4. Iso (1993). *ISO X50-660 Experimental Standard, Business Excellence, Business Employment, Method and Identification*. Afnor, 1st edition. Paris-La-Defense.
5. Ratier F. (1994). *Semantics for Analysis, From Linguistics to Computer Science*. Mason.
6. <https://succes-de-vente.fr>
7. <https://academie-des-sciences-commerciales.org>